

A Study on Job Satisfaction of Employees with Special Reference to Private Hospital in Dharmapuri

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A. Deepika, M.Com (CA), M.Phil.,

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce

Pachamuthu College of Arts & Science for Women, Dharmapuri

Abstract

Job satisfaction refers to a person's feeling of satisfaction on the job, which acts as a motivation to work. It is not self-satisfaction, happiness or self-contentment but satisfaction on the job. Human resources management means employing people, developing their resources, utilizing, maintaining and compensating their services in tune with job and organization requirements with a view to contribute to the goals of the organization, individual and the society. The study is to analyze the relation between job satisfaction and the performance of private hospital employees and identify the problems faced by an employee and give suggestions based on the research.

Introduction

Job satisfaction refers to a person's feeling of satisfaction on the job, which acts as a motivation to work. It is not self-satisfaction, happiness or self-contentment but satisfaction on the job.

The term relates to the total relationship between an individual and the employer for which he is paid satisfaction does mean the simple feeling, state accompanying the attainment of any goal, the end-state is feeling accompanying the attainment by an impulse of its objective. Job dissatisfaction does mean absence of motivation at work.

Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the satisfaction regarding the job factor.
2. To analyze the relation between job satisfaction and the performance of private hospital employees.

Scope of the Study

1. The study was conduct among the selective private hospital in Dharmapuri.
2. The study explores the views expressed by the respondents about motivation providing solution in the attempt to develop a better system in the hospital.

Limitations of the Study

1. The data have been collected from the present employee only. So it may vary in the future.
2. The duration of the study is limited. So it may not be able to cover the entire scope.
3. The study was restricted only in selected private hospitals in Dharmapuri.

Research Methodology

Research methodology is a way to systematically solving the research problems. Research methodology deals with the research design used and methods used to present the study.

Research Design

A research design is the arrangement of conditions for collections and analysis of data in the manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose with economy in procedure.

Sampling and Sample Size

The sample method used for this project is simple random sampling method which comes under probability sampling.

Simple Random Sampling

This type of sampling is also known as chance sampling or probability sampling where each item in the population has an equal chance of inclusion in the sample and each one possible samples, in case of finite universe, has the same probability of being selected. For this study, respondents were approached in random and their responses were recorded in the questionnaire provided to them.

Sample Size

Sample size refers to the number of the respondents included in the project. The sample size of the project is 56 employees. The entire population has been covered for the study.

Sources of Data

Both primary as well as secondary sources were utilized in this study. A well designed pretested questionnaire was used by the researcher to collect the necessary information from the respondents.

1. Primary data

The primary data are those which are collected for the first time and are fresh and thus happen to be original in character. Primary data may be made through either by complete enumeration or sampling survey method.

2. Secondary data

Secondary data refers to the data which is originally collected and published by the authorities other than who require it such data is already available in some government publication research study journals or newspapers.

Tools Used in this Study

Percentage analysis

Percentage analysis

Percentage analysis refers to a special type of ratio. Percentage is used in making comparison between two percentage analyses and two or more series of data.

Formula

Review of Literature

Karin and William (1990)¹ investigated how in store price promotions affect market share after the promotion have been retracted. They find that effects of promotion are contingent on both the choice pattern of subjects. Whether or not subjects switch in a product category.

Avis, Inman and, McAlister's (1992)³ that promotion do not effect brand evaluation can be understood better. They study categories with which consumer had considerable prior experience and which promotions were common. Furthermore, the brands they examine had been promoted in the past stores frequently use price promotions to attract customers.

Amber, T.(2003)⁸ may companies measure brand equity to ensure that marketing activities are aligned with the company's strategy and to ensure that investment is used for the right.

Marioka palazon (2005)⁹ adopted a consumer- based approach to consider that sales promotion as a part of marketing communication also have an effect at a cognitive and emotional level and provide the consumer with multiple hedonic and utilitarian benefits.

Nelson (2005)¹⁰ the impact of sales promotion tools, namely coupon price discount free sample bonus pack and in store displays on product trial and repurchase behavior of consumers.

Data Analysis and Interpretation**Table Respondents Opinion Regarding Working in Ward**

S. No	Working Ward	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Medical/ internal	16	29
2	Operating room	12	21
3	Surgical	9	16
4	Emergency ward	19	34
Total		56	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation

The above table 1 shows the 29% of the respondent are working in Medical/ internal ward, 21% of the respondents are working in Operating Room, 16% of the respondent are working in Surgical, and remaining 34% of the respondents are working in Emergency ward.

Majority (34%) of the respondents are working in Emergency ward.

Table Working Experience of the Respondents

S. No	Experience	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Below 3 years	12	21
2	3 to 5 years	22	39
3	5 to 10 years	16	29
4	Above 10 years	6	11
Total		56	100

Source: primary data

Interpretation

The above table 2 shows that the experience of the respondents among the total 56 respondents, 21% of the respondents total experience of below 3years, 39% of the respondents are said the experience 3 to 5 years, 29% of the respondents are said the experience is 5 to 10 years, 11% of the respondents belonged to the experience above 10 years.

Majority (39%) of the respondents are working experience between 3-5 years.

Table Respondents Relationship with Co-Workers

S.No	Co-Workers Relationship	No.of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Good	22	39
2	Very good	12	21
3	Poor	13	24
4	Very poor	9	16
Total		56	100

Source: primary data

Interpretation

The above table 3 of the respondents shows the co - workers relationship of the respondents in that 39% of the respondents are good, 21% of the respondents are very good, 23% of the respondents are poor and remaining 16% of the respondents are very poor. Majority (39%) of the respondents are said good relationship with co-worker.

Suggestions

1. By giving training & motivation management can develop more skill among the employees.
2. The hospital may encourage the workers through job for their awards & rewards.
3. The hospital may also give additional opportunity and training program for the workers if they prefer.

Conclusion

Hence we conclude, we have to say that job satisfaction is a very important aspect of employee's life. While the concept of job satisfaction is prevalent in the developed countries, there is still very little scope for expectation in the developing countries. However the job satisfaction is not significant with job itself and pride. The study draws conclusion that employee relationship with co-workers influences their satisfaction level. Hospital could clearly define the promotional opportunities.

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